

YIELD, NUTRIENT UPTAKE AND QUALITY OF CHICKPEA AS INFLUENCED BY POTASSIUM

Mane S. S.*; Chaudhari, A. A.; Ugile, S.K.; Jadhav, K.T. and Bhadane, D.T.,

Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry,

College of Agriculture, Badnapur

Vasantrao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth Parbhani 431 402 (M.S.), India

ssmane2013@gmail.com

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Abstract

A Field experiment was conducted during 2018-19 at College of Agriculture, Badnapur to study effect of potassium on Chickpea varieties. Amongst different varieties Phule Vikram was effective in recording highest growth parameters, yield attributes and yield. While Digvijay recorded maximum protein and seed index. The results emerged out clearly indicated that various parameters like plant height, dry matter kg ha⁻¹, protein, seed and straw yield, N, P, K uptake and its status after harvest was increased due to application of potassium. It was inferred from the results that application of RDF + Potassium @ 30 kg ha⁻¹ + 2 Foliar spray of KNO₃ @ 1% showed synergistic effects on nutrients (N, P and K) uptake. Soil fertility was also found to be improved due to application of potassium to chickpea varieties.

Keywords: Potassium Nitrate, Chick pea, foliar application, yield, NPK uptake.

Introduction

Potassium application is generally neglected, resulting to serious depletion of soil K reserves. Chickpea removes about 49.6 kg K₂O tonne⁻¹ grain, which is higher than nitrogen (46.3kg tonne⁻¹ grain) Velayutham and Reddy (1987). The crucial importance of K in quality formation confirms its role in promoting the production of photosynthates and their transport to storage organs such as fruits, grains and tubers and enhancing their conversion into starch, protein, vitamins and oil (Mengel and Kirkby, 2001). Foliar nutrition may be a useful option particularly for the areas where soil application of fertilizers often leads to leaching or loss of nutrients. Since chickpea is normally cultivated on relatively poor soil on residual soil moisture, it becomes imperative to study the effect of potassium on yield, nutrient uptake, quality and soil fertility.

Material and Methods

The experiment was conducted in factorial randomized block design with two factors viz., four varieties (V1-Digvijay, V2-BDNG-797, V3-JAKI-9218 and V4-Phule Vikram) and four fertilizer levels (Control i.e. RDF 25:50:00 kg NPK ha⁻¹ (F1), RDF + Potassium @ 30 kg ha⁻¹ (F2), RDF+ 2 Foliar spray of KNO₃ @ 1% at flowering and pod formation stage (F3), RDF+ Potassium @ 30 kg ha⁻¹ + 2 Foliar spray of KNO₃ @ 1% at flowering and pod formation stage (F4)) with 16 treatments combinations. Each experimental unit was replicated two times. Each treatment consisted of 15 rows with row to row spacing 30 cm. agronomic practices were carried out uniformly according to in all the treatments. Nitrogen concentration in plant samples was determined by the kjeldhal method (Piper, 1966). Phosphorous was estimated by vanadomolybdophosphoric acid yellow colour method prepared using spectrophotometer, Jackson (1973). Potassium was determined on flame photometer as suggested by Jackson (1973). Protein content was estimated by seed nitrogen per cent was multiplied by the factor of 6.25 to get the percentage of protein in chickpea seed. Nutrient uptake i.e. uptake of N, P, K, was calculated by considering grain and dry matter yield at harvest in particular treatment plot in relation concentration of the particular nutrient in respective treatment plot using the formula.

$$\text{Nutrient concentration \% X (dry matter yield (kg ha}^{-1}\text{))}$$

$$\text{Uptake (kg ha}^{-1}\text{)} = \frac{\text{---}}{\text{---}}$$

100

Results and Discussion**Protein content:**

The data presented in table 1 indicates significant impact of potassium on protein (%) in chickpea seed. Amongst the varieties, Digvijay recorded maximum protein (19.15%) however which was at par with Phule Vikram (19.03%). significantly lowest protein was recorded due to JAKI-9218 (18.11%). Amongst various fertilizer levels significantly maximum protein (20.86%) was observed under

fertilizer level (F4) RDF + Potassium @ 30 kg ha⁻¹ + 2 Foliar spray of KNO₃ @ 1% at flowering and pod formation stage which was followed by fertilizer level (F2) and (F3). Significantly lowest protein (15.88%) was recorded with fertilizer level (F1) Control (RDF-25:50:00 kg NPK ha⁻¹). Similar finding also recorded by Farhad *et al.* (2010) concluded that application of potassium @ 40 kg ha⁻¹ produced the highest protein content in soybean.

Grain yield :

Amongst the varieties, Phule Vikram recorded maximum grain yield (1062.76 kg ha⁻¹) which was significantly superior over Digvijay (978.07 kg ha⁻¹), BDNG-797 (963.85 kg ha⁻¹) and JAKI-9218 (924.23 kg ha⁻¹). Amongst fertilizer levels (F4) RDF + Potassium @ 30 kg ha⁻¹ + 2 Foliar spray of KNO₃ @ 1% at flowering and pod formation stage recorded significantly highest yield (1022.88 kg ha⁻¹) than fertilizer level (F1) Control (RDF-25:50:00 kg NPK ha⁻¹) (909.72 kg ha⁻¹) and was at par with fertilizer level (F2) RDF + Potassium @ 30 kg ha⁻¹ (1005.87 kg ha⁻¹) and fertilizer level (F3) RDF+ 2 Foliar spray of KNO₃ @ 1% at flowering and pod formation stage (990.47 kg ha⁻¹). Significantly lowest grain yield was recorded with fertilizer level (F1) Control (RDF-25:50:00 kg NPK ha⁻¹) (909.72 kg ha⁻¹) at harvest. The positive effect of K on crop yield might also be due to its requirement in carbohydrate synthesis and translocation of photosynthesis and also may be due to improved yield attributing characters, shoot growth and nodulation. These results also confirmed with the findings of Adsure *et al.*, (2018) in black gram.

Uptake of nutrients:

Significantly highest uptake of N, P and K was recorded due to Phule Vikram followed by Digvijay and BDNG-797 respectively. Significantly lowest uptake of N was recorded due to JAKI-9218. Similarly highest uptake of N, P and K was recorded due to application of (F4) i.e. RDF + Potassium @ 30 kg ha⁻¹ + 2 Foliar spray of KNO₃ @ 1% at flowering and pod formation stage which was at par with fertilizer level (F2) RDF + Potassium @ 30 kg ha⁻¹. While significantly lowest uptake of N, P and K was recorded due to fertilizer level (F1) Control (RDF-25:50:00 kg NPK ha⁻¹).

An increase in N uptake in presence of potassium, could be attributed to enhanced vigour of crop growth with increased utilization and translocation of N in to plant and synergetic effect between N and K in soil system resulting in the enhancement of yield. similar results were also recorded by Gaud *et al.* (2014).

Interaction effect : Interaction effect due to different varieties and fertilizer levels in respect of N, P and K was found to be non-significant in chickpea.

Effect of potassium on available N, P and K in soil after harvest of crop : Significantly higher values of available N and K status in soil after harvest of chickpea due to fertilizer level (F4) RDF+ Potassium @ 30 kg ha⁻¹ + 2 Foliar spray of KNO₃ @ 1% at flowering and pod formation stage, which was statistically at par with fertilizer level (F2) RDF + Potassium @ 30 kg ha⁻¹ respectively. However, significantly highest values of P status in soil after harvest of

chickpea due to fertilizer level (F₄) over the fertilizer levels (F₁), (F₂) and (F₃) respectively. Significant variations by addition of potassium are attributed to higher availability and absorption of nutrient. Similar results were also reported by Gaud et al. (2014)

Interaction effect: Interaction effect due to different varieties and fertilizer levels was found to be non-significant for available N, P and K in soil after harvest of chickpea.

References:

1. **Adsure VK, Mane SS, Supekar SJ 2018.** Effect of graded levels of potassium on yield and major nutrient uptake of black gram. *IJCS* 2018; 6(2):2980-2982.
2. **Farhad, I.S., M., Islam, M.N., Hoque, S. and Bhuiyan, M.S.I. (2010).** Role of potassium and sulphur on the growth, yield and oil content of soybean (*Glycine max* L.). *Academic Journal of Plant Sciences.*, 3(2) : 99-103.
3. **Gaud, V.V.; Konde, N. M.; Mohod, P. V. and Kharche, V. K. 2014.** Response of chickpea to potassium fertilization on yield, quality, soil fertility and economic in vertisols. *Legume Research*, 37(3): 311-315.
4. **Jackson, M.L. (1973).** Soil Chemical Analysis Prentice Hall Inc., Englant Cliffs, New Jersey.
5. **Mane S. S.*; Chaudhari, A. A.; Ugile, S.K.; Jadhav, K.T. and Bhadane, D.T.,** Yield, Nutrient Uptake And Quality Of Chickpea As Influenced By Potassium , Vol. Xiii, Issue Xxxviii, Nov To Jan 2024 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, pp 196-198.

6. **Mengel, K. and Kirkby, E. A. (2001).** *Principles of plant nutrition.* Dordrecht, the Netherlands: Kluwer Academic Publishers.
7. **N.P. Talokar^{1*}, U.U. Rajput² Mrinalini C. Uikay³ and S.A. Borde** Effect Of Broad Bed Furrow Method For Irrigated Chickpea In Buldana District Of Maharashtra, Vol. Xii, Issue Xxxii, April 2022 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, pp 52-53.
8. **Om Prakash Prajapat¹, Surendra Singh² and Lala Ram Yadav³,** Nitrogen, Phosphorus Content And Uptake With Their Interactive Effect On Chickpea (*Cicer Arietinum* L.) As Influenced By Different Liquid Biofertilizers Under Varying Fertility Levels , Vol. Xiii, Issue Xxxvii, July 2023 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, pp 929-932.
9. **Piper, C.S. (1966).** Soil and plant analysis. Inter Science Publisher Inc. *New York Philips-Journal.*
10. **Raghavendra Yaligar, Jyothi R, Narappa G, Farzan M.K, Mahantesha M T, Kavita, Ullikashi And Radha .J** Integrated Disease Management In Chickpea Under Front Line Demonstration Of Koppal District, Vol. Xii, Issue Xxxv, Jan 2023 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601 , Pp 442-443.
11. **Velayutham, M. and Reddy, K.C.K. (1987).** Balanced fertilization for increasing fertilizer use efficiency. Pages 39-45 in Proceeding of the IFA regional agricultural meeting, 8-12 Dec 1986, New Delhi. IFA Ltd., 28 rue Marbeuf, Paris.

Table 1 : Effect of different varieties and fertilizer levels on grain and straw yield ,protein , NPK uptake and available NPK after harvest.

Treatments		Grain yield kg ha ⁻¹	Straw yield kg ha ⁻¹	Protein %	N uptake Kg ha ⁻¹	P uptake Kg ha ⁻¹	K uptake Kg ha	Available N (kg ha ⁻¹)	Available P (kg ha ⁻¹)	Available K (kg ha ⁻¹)
Varieties										
V ₁	Digvijay	978.07	1528.14	19.15	51.08	7.69	29.17	187.76	21.09	790.42
V ₂	BDNG-797	963.85	1465.10	18.50	48.71	7.23	27.52	192.84	21.53	790.82
V ₃	JAKI-9218	924.23	1382.30	18.11	47.00	6.93	26.39	188.52	20.75	797.05
V ₄	Phule vikram	1062.76	1726.76	19.03	57.61	8.66	32.64	194.96	21.50	803.93
SE ±		23.19	23.98	0.08	1.60	1.60	0.25	0.93	0.27	6.09
CD at 5 %		69.90	72.26	0.24	4.82	4.82	0.74	2.80	NS	NS
Fertilizer levels										
F ₁	Control (RDF-25:50:00 kg NPK ha ⁻¹)	909.72	1463.68	15.88	42.63	5.62	25.23	178.09	18.33	737.97
F ₂	RDF + Potassium @ 30 kg ha ⁻¹	1005.87	1506.23	19.88	54.93	8.40	30.11	197.19	21.76	828.60
F ₃	RDF+ 2 Foliar spray of KNO ₃ @ 1% at flowering & pod formation stag	990.47	1547.36	18.18	50.08	7.45	28.48	187.26	20.68	770.38
F ₄	RDF + Potassium @ 30 kg ha ⁻¹ + 2 Foliar spray of KNO ₃ @ 1% at flowering and pod formation stage	1022.88	1585.02	20.86	56.75	9.04	31.90	201.55	24.10	845.27
SE ±		23.19	23.98	0.08	1.60	0.25	0.93	2.38	0.27	6.09
CD at 5 %		69.90	72.26	0.24	4.82	0.74	2.80	7.16	0.82	18.36
Interaction (VXF)										
SE ±		46.38	47.95	0.15	3.19	0.49	1.85	4.75	0.54	12.18
CD at 5 %		NS	NS	6.21	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
General Mean		982.23	1525.57	18.69	51.09	7.62	28.93	191.01	21.21	795.55